

Impact of Ethiopia's 2015 drought on child undernutrition

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ABSTRACT

In 2015, Ethiopia experienced one of its worst droughts in decades. Using nationally representative data from before and after the event, we do not find evidence that this drought led to widespread increases in chronic or acute child undernutrition. However, further analysis indicates that chronic undernutrition rates did increase in drought-exposed areas that had a limited road network. This finding suggests that the recent investments in road infrastructure in Ethiopia may have contributed towards better resilience against droughts.

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1. Introduction

Despite significant progress over the last decade, child undernutrition rates in Africa remain high constituting one of the continent's main development challenges. In 2018, one-third of children under-five in Africa were chronically undernourished (stunted; short for their age) while an estimated seven percent were acutely undernourished (wasted; low weight for their height) (UNICEF, WHO, & World Bank Group, 2018)¹. Poor nutrition in early life is associated with impaired cognitive development and linked to lower human capital attainment, life expectancy and lower socio-economic status in adulthood (Barker, Porslove, & Robinson, 1992; Almond & Currie, 2011; Hoddinott et al., 2013). Considering all these dimensions, Galasso and Wagstaff (2019) estimate that the average per capita income penalty from childhood stunting is 9–10 percent for sub-Saharan Africa.

Given the adverse long-term effects of early childhood malnutrition, researchers and policy-makers have been concerned with potential long-run impacts of temporary shocks. If an adverse shock worsens nutritional outcomes, and if poor nutrition is causally linked to worse socio-economic outcomes later in life, then a temporary shock can have consequences that last for a lifetime. An emerging body of research shows how short-term shocks in early childhood shape economic outcomes in adulthood.

Alderman, Hoddinott, and Kinsey (2006) find that exposure to civil war and drought shocks in early childhood led to decrease in adult stature and educational attainment in Zimbabwe. Maccini and Yang (2009) find that above-average rainfall in early life translated to better health, schooling and wealth status for adult women in Indonesia. Historical studies from 19th century Europe document similar findings. Lindeboom, Portrait, and Van den Berg (2010) find that exposure to the 1846–1847 Potato Famine in the Netherlands reduced life-expectancy at age 50 by approximately 3 years. Banerjee, Duflo, Postel-Vinay, and Watts (2010) find that children exposed to an agricultural income shock in late 19th century France grew as shorter adults than their peers, though they did not document other health or mortality effects. Even economic shocks in *in-utero* have been found to affect child's long-term socio-economic prospects (Stein, 1975; Almond, 2006; Almond, Edlund, Li, & Zhang, 2007; Miller, 2017; Bundervoet & Fransen, 2018; Beshir & Maystadt, 2019).

These long-term impacts of temporary shocks are particularly worrying considering that climate change is expected to increase the frequency of extreme weather events in Africa and elsewhere (Van Aalst, 2006; Dai, 2013; Hoegh-Guldberg et al., 2018; Grothe et al., 2019). Therefore, understanding how the impacts of weather shocks can be mitigated is key for designing policies and interventions to build resilience to climate change. This question is particularly relevant for Ethiopia, a country still remembered by the widespread drought and conflict triggered famines in the 1970s and 1980s, which had highly adverse short and long-term consequences (Webb & Braun, 1994; Dercon & Porter, 2014; Tafere, 2016; De Waal, 2017). Even less widespread droughts in the 1990s in rural Ethiopia had considerable – and persistent – impacts on child growth outcomes (Yamano, Alderman, & Christiaensen,

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¹ Wasting rates in Ethiopia and elsewhere fluctuate considerably across seasons and therefore wasting prevalence estimates based on a single season can be misleading (Baye & Hirvonen, 2020).

2005) and household consumption (Dercon, 2004; Dercon, Hoddinott, & Woldehanna, 2005; Porter, 2012).²

In this paper, we examine the impact of the 2015 *El Nino* induced drought on child undernutrition and the mitigating role played by improved connectivity through transport infrastructure. The 2015 drought was labeled as the worst drought in decades and resulted in failure of two consecutive rainy seasons, poor harvests in the eastern parts of the country, and led to a sharp increase in humanitarian requirements with more than 10 million Ethiopians in need of food aid³ (NDRMC, 2016). Despite the perceived severity of the drought, we cannot reject the hypothesis that the drought did not have a negative impact on children's heights (relative to age) or weights (relative to height), measured approximately six months after the drought. These results are robust to different ways of defining drought.

In trying to explain this perhaps surprising finding, we focus on the role of transport infrastructure in alleviating the effect of shocks. Since 2000, Ethiopia has made massive investments in transport infrastructure, both in long-distance trunk roads and, since 2010, in rural roads that aim to connect each *kebele* (sub-district) to an all-weather road (World Bank, 2016).⁴ As a result, 25 percent of the population resided within one hour travel time to a town of at least 50,000 people in 2015, up from 9 percent in 1994 (Schmidt et al., 2018). Similarly, the share that had to travel more than 10 h to reach a town of this size decreased from 29 percent to 5 percent over the same period (Schmidt et al., 2018). Interacting drought exposure with road access, we find that the 2015 drought increased chronic child undernutrition in areas characterized by limited primary road networks, but that this effect was muted in places with better road connectivity. We interpret these findings as evidence that improved connectivity through investments in transport infrastructure may improve resilience in rural drought-affected communities.

The findings of this paper complement other recent research findings on the importance of rural connectivity in Ethiopia. Hill and Fuje (2016) show how the impact of droughts on food prices has weakened over time, mainly due to better market access through improved road infrastructure and better drought management. Stifel, Minten, and Koru (2016) estimate an internal rate of return for rural roads in Ethiopia of between 12 and 35 percent. Nakamura, Bundervoet, and Nuru (2020) assess the government's Universal Rural Road Access Project and find that households in communities that were connected with a road during the project were shielded from the worst effects of the 2015 drought. Miller (2017) finds suggestive evidence that road infrastructure mitigates the negative impact of food scarcity during pregnancy on child's later health outcomes in Ethiopia. Abay and Hirvonen (2017) and Headey, Hirvonen, Hoddinott, and Stifel (2019) find that better market access is associated with better child diets. Taken together, these findings suggest that improved transport infrastructure, particularly in rural areas, will be key in building the resilience of rural and agricultural communities to increasingly frequent weather shocks.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of the context. In Section 3, we discuss the data used in the analysis and present some descriptive analysis. Section 4 outlines the econometric strategy, and Section 5 presents the results. In

Section 6 we assess heterogeneity by road access. Section 7 concludes.

2. Context

About 80 percent of the near 100 million Ethiopians reside in rural areas and more than 80 percent of the adult population engage in agricultural activities (Central Statistical Agency [Ethiopia], 2005, 2010). Ethiopian farmers mainly rely on rain-fed agriculture (Awulachew, Erkossa, & Namara, 2010), and as a result, agricultural output remains highly vulnerable to weather anomalies. The main agricultural areas of the country have two rainy seasons. The small rainy season (*belg*) typically occurs between March and May and the main rainy season (*meher*) between June and September. *Meher* is the most important season for agricultural production with more than 90 percent of the total cereal production in the country taking place during this season (Taffesse, Dorosh, & Gemessa, 2012).

To date, a small number of studies has attempted to understand the welfare impacts of the 2015 drought in Ethiopia (Sohnesen, 2019). The Central Statistical Agency (CSA) of Ethiopia estimates that, compared to the previous year, the grain production in the country decreased only by 1.3 percent (3.5 million quintals) during the main agricultural season (*meher*) in 2015 (CSA, 2016). Of note, however, is that this national level estimate masks considerable regional variation. The grain output in Oromia and Amhara – the two regions responsible for about 80 percent of the total grain production in the country – remained the same compared to the previous season. At the same time, production fell by 66 percent in Afar, 30 percent in the Gambella region, 25 percent in Somale and 10 percent in Tigray (CSA, 2016). Mann, Warner, and Malik (2019) also point out that the 2015 drought mainly hit areas characterized by chronic food insecurity and low agricultural production. Moreover, Bachewe, Yimer, Minten, and Dorosh (2016) find no evidence of large-scale effects of the drought on cereal prices. The analysis carried out by Dorosh, Smart, Minten, and Stifel (2018) suggests that the reason why major price hikes did not occur was due to a combination of massive imports of humanitarian food-aid⁵ and considerable inflows of food from surplus areas of the country. This implies that cereal markets in Ethiopia are relatively well integrated⁶ – at least when it comes to the main regional markets from which these monthly cereal price data are collected from.

3. Data and descriptive analysis

Our data come from the Ethiopian Socioeconomic Survey (ESS). ESS is a longitudinal survey conducted by the Central Statistics Agency of Ethiopia (CSA) and the World Bank Living Standards Measurement Study – Integrated Surveys on Agriculture (LSMS-ISA) team (CSA & The World Bank, 2013, 2015). ESS spans three rounds: 2012, 2014 and 2016.⁷

For the current study, we use the latest two rounds of data from 2014 and 2016 to compare anthropometric outcomes (heights, weights) of a cohort of young children before (2014) and after (2016) the 2015 drought. The household surveys and anthropometric measurements took place between February and April in

² De Waal (2017) provides a useful overview of the history of famines and droughts in Ethiopia arguing that the country's resilience against droughts has considerably increased over the past decade or so due to better overall preparedness and sizable investments in economic transformation, market infrastructure, and safety nets.

³ This number does not include people benefitting from the Productive Safety Net Program of Ethiopia, a geographically widespread safety net program covering about eight million people.

⁴ The federal and regional road network increased from 26,500 km in 1997 to 100,000 km in 2015 (World Bank, 2016).

⁵ The humanitarian response in 2015/16 was led by the Government of Ethiopia and supported by international donors and Non-Government Organizations (NGOs), and was relatively well targeted to areas exposed to the drought (Sohnesen, 2019).

⁶ This corresponds to the earlier work on cereal markets in Ethiopia (Rashid & Negassa, 2011; Minten et al., 2014).

⁷ The 2012 round is representative of rural and small-town areas of the country, the two recent ones are representative of the whole country, including large urban areas.

both survey rounds. Moreover, the survey is widespread having been implemented in all 11 administrative regions of Ethiopia. As a result, our data set covers communities that were seriously exposed to the 2015 drought and communities that were less exposed. Our difference in difference approach exploits both the temporal nature and the wide geographical coverage of the survey. We restrict the analysis to rural areas, as rural populations are highly reliant on rainfed agriculture for their main livelihood. Further details on sampling can be found in [CSA, NBE, and The World Bank \(2017\)](#).

One of the key decisions in this type of analysis is how to measure drought.⁸ Previous literature from Ethiopia has adopted a variety of measures to capture weather anomalies ranging from respondent self-reports ([Dercon et al., 2005](#); [Porter, 2012](#); [Dercon & Porter, 2014](#)) to weather observations obtained from local weather stations or satellites ([Yamano et al., 2005](#); [Thiede, 2014](#)).

For our main drought measure⁹, we use the Climate Hazards Group InfraRed Precipitation with Station data (CHIRPS) rainfall estimates (see [Funk et al., 2015](#)).¹⁰ These data come with different spatial and temporal resolutions. We opt for a spatial resolution of around 5 km (at the equator) and a temporal resolution of one month. We then merge these rainfall data with household latitude and longitude coordinates using an inverse-distance weighted average of the four nearest satellite observations. Following previous literature, we calculate Z-score deviations of rainfall during the *meher* season (June–September), in relation to long-term average in the same locality.¹¹

[Fig. 1](#) maps this Z-score value together with the survey locations (enumeration areas). We see that the central and northeast parts of the country were particularly severely hit by the drought. [Fig. 2](#) shows how the total rainfall during the *meher* season was well below historical averages. Compared to historical rainfalls, the rainfall during the *belg* season was also below average but less so compared to the *meher* season. In what follows we define drought-exposed areas as those for which the annual rainfall during the *meher* season was below -2 standard deviations. Assuming a normal distribution, such a drought occurs approximately once in every 40 years, on average.

The survey instrument also included a module on shocks that the household experienced in the past 12 months. [Table 1](#) shows how the share of households reporting a drought shock increased markedly between 2014 and 2016 in areas exposed to the 2015 drought (based on the CHIRPS rainfall data).¹² Elsewhere in the questionnaire, the respondents were asked whether, in the last 12 months, they experienced a situation where they did not have enough food to feed the household. Interestingly, food security improved in this sample between 2014 and 2016 despite the drought ([Table 2](#)). Moreover, regional comparison of [Tables 1 and 2](#) suggests

that the 2015 drought did not substantially increase (self-reported) food insecurity in drought-exposed areas.

The survey team took anthropometric measures (height and weight) of children between 6 and 59 months of age in all rounds. We converted these data – children’s heights and weights – into Z-scores using the WHO growth standards ([WHO, 2006](#); [de Onis et al., 2007](#)). These growth standards permit us to assess child height and weight relative to well-nourished children of the same age and sex.¹³ As our main outcome variables, we use height-for-age Z-score (HAZ) and weight-for-height Z-score (WHZ). Low HAZ is a marker for chronic undernutrition – an outcome of prolonged inadequate food intake or infection. Programmatically, children are considered chronically undernourished (stunted) if their HAZ is below -2 . In contrast, low WHZ value is a marker for acute undernutrition capturing inadequate nutritional intakes during the period immediately before the measurements. Children whose WHZ is below -2 are classified as wasted. While child stunting and wasting share some of the same causal factors (e.g. inadequate diet, infectious diseases) ([Martorell & Young, 2012](#)), the direct relationship between them remains poorly understood ([Khara & Dolan, 2014](#); [ENN, 2018](#)). The available evidence suggests that past weight fluctuations translate into increased risk of linear growth faltering ([Richard et al., 2012](#); [Schoenbuchner et al., 2019](#); [Wells et al., 2019](#)).¹⁴

[Fig. 3a](#) shows the HAZ-age relationship for the cohort measured in 2014 (before the drought) and cohort measured in 2016 (after the drought). First, we see that the children in our sample follow the usual dynamics of growth faltering observed in other low income countries ([Victora et al., 2010](#)): HAZ declines rapidly during the first 2 years of life after which it stabilizes. Second, for almost all age groups, the average HAZ curve for 2016 lies above the corresponding curve for the 2014 cohort. While the confidence intervals overlap, this suggest that the impacts of the 2015 drought on chronic undernutrition were – if anything – marginal. [Fig. 3b](#) shows the same relationship for WHZ. Again, there is little convincing evidence that the post-drought cohort is worse-off compared to the pre-drought cohort.

[Fig. 4a](#) further displays the HAZ distributions for both cohorts. Both distributions are skewed to the right. The distributions lie almost on top of each other again suggesting that the 2015 drought did not have a widespread impact on children’s HAZ scores. [Fig. 4b](#) shows the same for WHZ.

In [Fig. 5a](#) we look at the association between the HAZ scores in 2016 and rainfall Z-score in 2015. The local polynomial regression line is nearly flat implying that children residing in drought exposed areas did not have worse HAZ scores in 2016 compared to children who were not (or were less) exposed to the 2015 drought. The same local polynomial regression based on WHZ also shows a relatively a flat relationship between WHZ and rainfall Z-score ([Fig. 5b](#)). However, we see a small increase for the better part of the rainfall distribution (rainfall Z-score > -1). In the subsequent sections, we test whether the story arising from these simple associations holds when we control for various factors that may be correlated with children’s anthropometric outcomes and drought exposure.

4. Methods

The data available to us give rise to a difference in difference (DiD) estimator (see e.g. [Meyer, 1995](#)). The DiD estimator requires

⁸ [Sohnesen \(2019\)](#) illustrates this point using the same household survey data for Ethiopia.

⁹ We consider several alternative drought measures in Appendix B.

¹⁰ For a given geographical area, the quality of the weather data depends on the number of active weather stations. Across the globe, including Africa, the number of active weather stations has been in steady decline over the past decades ([Lorenz & Kunstmann, 2012](#)). Thus, satellite observations provide a valuable resource for areas with a sparse station network.

¹¹ More specifically, the rainfall Z-scores were computed by taking the total rainfall observed in the 2015 *meher* season (June–September) for the household and subtracting the long-term (2000–2015) mean for the household’s locality from this 2015 value. We then divide this subtraction with the standard deviation calculated from the 2000–2015 rainfall time-series for the same household. In order to minimize the role of measurement error in household GPS-coordinates, we further take the mean Z-score at the enumeration area (EA) level.

¹² It is likely that households are more likely to report shocks that had a negative welfare effect on them ([Dex, 1995](#); [De Weerd, 2008](#)). If so, this will lead to an upward bias in estimating the negative welfare impacts of droughts. It is for this reason, we measure drought using satellite observations. However, in Appendix B we show that our results are also robust to defining drought using household self-reports.

¹³ We used the user-written *zanthro06* command ([Leroy, 2011](#)) in Stata 15.0 to construct the Z-scores. Z-score values below -5 and above $+5$ were considered as biologically implausible and not used in the analysis.

¹⁴ In the highland regions of Ethiopia, wasting prevalence is generally higher during the dry season (January–April) compared to the wet season (June–September) ([Egata, Berhane, & Worku, 2013](#); [Roba et al., 2016](#); [Baye & Hirvonen, 2020](#)).

Fig. 1. Rainfall deviations (Z-score) during the *meher* season in 2015 Source: Authors' calculation from CHIRPS rainfall data. The dark dots are survey locations (Enumeration Areas).

Fig. 2. Distribution of rainfall (Z-score) in 2015 in the sample.

compare the change in anthropometric outcomes in 2014 and 2016 between the treated and un-treated cohorts of children.¹⁵

More formally, we use the following specification to model the anthropometric outcome (height-for-age or weight-for-height Z-score) of a child i residing in enumeration area (EA) w of region r and observed in year t (Y_{irwt}):

$$Y_{irwt} = \beta_1 D_{irw} + \beta_2 (T_t * D_{irw}) + (T_t * R_r)' \delta + X'_{irw} \gamma + \omega + \varepsilon_{irwt} \quad (1)$$

where D_{irw} is a binary variable capturing a value of 1 if the 2015 rainfall Z-score for the EA was below -2 and zero otherwise. T_t is a binary variable obtaining a value of 0 if survey year is 2014 and 1 if the survey year is 2016 and R_r is a vector of binary variables for each region. The interaction of these two sets of variables ($T_t * R_r$) controls for region specific time trends. The impact of the drought on child's HAZ or WHZ is measured by β_2 ; the coefficient on the interaction between D_{irw} and T_t variables.

data for at least two time periods and from both the treated and un-treated groups. Here, the 'treated group' refers to the cohorts of children who reside in drought exposed areas and the 'un-treated group' to the cohorts of children who reside in other, non-exposed, areas. For both groups, we have observations before (i.e., 2014) and after the drought (i.e., 2016). As a result, we can

¹⁵ Of note is that conventional panel methods (i.e. child or household level fixed effects) are not suited to this exercise. This is because children 'age-out' of the sample; the older children observed in 2014 were not measured in 2016. Moreover, growth faltering typically occurs in the first two years of life (Victoria et al., 2010) and therefore studying the impacts on older children is considered less informative. It is for this reason that randomized controlled trials involving children in the nutrition literature are often based on cohort comparisons (or repeated cross-sections), rather than on longitudinal samples.

Table 1

Share of households exposed to drought, by source and region.

Data source:	CHIRPS	Household self-reports:		
		2014-round	2016-round	difference
Region	2015			
Afar	0.44	0.14	0.72	0.58
Amhara	0.59	0.11	0.27	0.17
Benishangul Gumuz	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Dire Dawa	0.94	0.23	0.82	0.59
Gambella	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.07
Harari	0.63	0.01	0.77	0.76
Oromia	0.26	0.07	0.23	0.16
SNNP	0.04	0.03	0.24	0.21
Somali	0.07	0.51	0.75	0.24
Tigray	0.12	0.14	0.41	0.27

Note: These estimates are based on sampling weights. Rainfall shock in CHIRPS column is defined as rainfall Z-score below -2 standard deviations from the long-term mean. SNNP = Southern Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples' Region.

Table 2

Share of households reporting hunger in the past 12 months, by survey round and region.

Region	2014-round	2016-round	Difference
Afar	0.17	0.24	0.06
Amhara	0.33	0.16	-0.18
Benishangul Gumuz	0.33	0.17	-0.16
Dire Dawa	0.50	0.40	-0.10
Gambella	0.11	0.22	0.11
Harari	0.15	0.16	0.01
Oromia	0.29	0.33	0.04
SNNP	0.47	0.48	0.01
Somali	0.46	0.47	0.02
Tigray	0.33	0.22	-0.11
All regions	0.35	0.31	-0.04

Note: These estimates are based on sampling weights. SNNP = Southern Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples' Region.

Furthermore, X'_{irw} is a vector of child and household specific characteristics; spline function of child age in months¹⁶ and sex, household size, the dependency ratio¹⁷, highest education level in household, as well as the gender and age of the household head.¹⁸ We also include EA fixed effects (ω) to the equation that control for time-invariant characteristics fixed to the EA. The last term in the equation, ε_{irwt} , is the error term. Finally, we cluster our standard errors at the EA level.

After dropping children with missing observations, we have 1874 children from the 2014 survey round and 1708 children from the 2016 survey round. These children group into 290 EAs in all regions of Ethiopia, excluding Addis Ababa, which is the only entirely urban region.

Table 3 provides summary statistics for 2014 for children residing in areas that were not exposed and children residing in areas that were exposed, respectively, to the 2015 drought. Comparison

¹⁶ Due to inadequate diets or repeated infections (or both), rapid growth faltering typically occurs in the first 2 years of life. As a result, HAZ has a non-linear relationship with child age (Victora et al., 2010), roughly until the 24 months after which the HAZ scores stabilize. Failure to model this properly may lead to biased estimates of β_2 (Cummins, 2013). Here, we model this relationship using a spline function of child's age in months with knots at 12, 18 and 24 months.

¹⁷ Dependency ratio is calculated by adding the number of household members who are less than 15 years and the number of household members who are above 65 years and dividing this sum with the total number of household members.

¹⁸ We are careful not to include variables that may have been affected by the treatment (drought). For example, households in Ethiopia typically respond to shocks by selling off their assets; e.g. livestock and durable assets. Including variables that could be considered themselves as outcome variables are labelled as 'bad controls' in the literature. The inclusion of such variables mean that the coefficient on our treatment variable would no longer have a causal interpretation (see Angrist & Pischke, 2009, p. 64–68).

Fig. 3a. Height-for-age Z-score by child age Note: Local polynomial regression. Sample is formed of 1913 children 6–59 months in 2014 and 1745 children 6–59 months in 2016 round. The grey vertical bars represent 95%-confidence intervals.

Fig. 3b. Weight-for-height Z-score by child age Note: Sample is formed of 1998 children 6–59 months in 2014 and 1854 children 6–59 months in 2016 round. The grey vertical bars represent 95%-confidence intervals.

of the summary statistics across the two sub-samples shows that the sample is well balanced for our outcome variable: the difference in the anthropometric outcomes (HAZ, stunting, WHZ, wasting) are not statistically different from zero. This suggests that the 2015 drought did not hit (sampled) localities that had higher

Fig. 4a. Height-for-age Z-score distributions by survey round Note: Sample is formed of 1913 children 6–59 months in 2014 and 1745 children 6–59 months in 2016 round.

Fig. 4b. Weight-for-Height Z-score distributions by survey round Note: Sample is formed of 1998 children 6–59 months in 2014 and 1854 children 6–59 months in 2016 round.

Fig. 5a. Association between children’s HAZ in 2016 and rainfall in 2015 Note: Local polynomial regression. Sample: 1745 children 6–59 months in 2016 round. The grey vertical bars represent 95%-confidence intervals. Dashed lines represent bottom and top 5% of the rainfall Z-score distribution.

Fig. 5b. Association between children’s WHZ in 2016 and rainfall in 2015 Note: Local polynomial regression. Sample: 1854 children 6–59 months in 2016 round. The grey vertical bars represent 95%-confidence intervals. Dashed lines represent bottom and top 5% of the rainfall Z-score distribution.

(or lower) chronic or acute undernutrition rates to begin with. However, we do see differences in some household characteristics. Households residing in localities that were exposed to the 2015 drought had marginally lower dependency ratios, older household heads, and better access to electricity and safe water sources but poorer access to toilets. In what follows, we control for these differences in our regression analysis.

In [Appendix A](#), we test the parallel trends assumption; that the drought exposed and non-exposed areas were on a similar trend before the 2015 drought. We conduct this test using pre-drought data from 2012 and 2014 ESS rounds to estimate Eq. (1). The results are reported in [Tables A1 and A2](#). The coefficient on the interaction term (β_2) is never statistically significant indicating that the child undernutrition trends were similar prior to 2015 across localities that were exposed to the 2015 drought and those that were not (after controlling for observed child and household characteristics, and EA fixed effects).

5. Results

[Table 4](#) provides the results. We estimate Eq. (1) using different subsets of controls to explore sensitivity of our point estimates. First, column 1 estimates Eq. (1) without controls for child and household level characteristics (X'_{hw}) or EA level fixed effects (ω). In column 2, we include EA level fixed effects to the specification estimated in column 1. In column 3, we add the child and household level controls but exclude the EA level fixed effects. Finally, column 4 provides the results based on the full specification based on Eq. (1).

In panel A we use HAZ as our outcome variable. The β_2 coefficient capturing the impact of the drought appears with a *a priori* correct sign in all columns; children residing in areas exposed to the drought have lower height-for-age Z-scores. Comparing the β_2 coefficients in columns 1 and 3 to the corresponding coefficients in columns 2 and 4, we see that adding EA fixed effects to the model slightly weakens the magnitude of the coefficient in absolute terms. Controlling for observed child and household level characteristics has the opposite effect (Columns 1-2 vs Column 3-4). More importantly, irrespective of the set of controls we have in the model, the magnitude of the β_2 coefficient is small and never statistically different from zero.¹⁹ This means that we cannot reject

¹⁹ The p-values range between 0.310 and 0.586 across the four columns in Panel A.

Table 3
Summary statistics in 2014 (before the drought).

	Non-drought Mean (std. dev.)	Drought Mean (std. dev.)	Difference
Height-for-age Z-score (HAZ)	-1.502 (1.764)	-1.537 (1.635)	0.035
Child is stunted (0/1)	0.413 (0.492)	0.407 (0.492)	0.006
Weight-for-height Z-score (WHZ)	-0.469 (1.408)	-0.401 (1.354)	-0.068
Child is wasted (0/1)	0.118 (0.323)	0.0964 (0.295)	0.022
Age in months	33.44 (15.21)	34.06 (15.17)	-0.620
Female child (0/1)	0.496 (0.500)	0.482 (0.500)	0.014
Household size	6.252 (2.097)	6.198 (1.901)	0.054
Dependency ratio	0.590 (0.133)	0.573 (0.126)	0.017**
Highest level of education (in years) in household	4.290 (3.369)	4.248 (3.411)	0.042
Female headed household (0/1)	0.111 (0.314)	0.0867 (0.282)	0.024
Age of the household head	38.63 (11.26)	40.34 (11.79)	-1.710***
Household has access to electricity (0/1)	0.137 (0.344)	0.224 (0.417)	-0.087***
Household has access to safe water source (0/1)	0.528 (0.499)	0.573 (0.495)	-0.045*
Household uses a toilet (0/1)	0.570 (0.495)	0.470 (0.500)	0.100***
Number of observations (children 6–59 months)	1459	415	

Note: (0/1) indicates a binary (dummy) variable. Equality in means tested using a two-sample *t* test with unequal variances. Statistical significance noted at *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$. Standard deviations in parentheses.

Table 4
The impact of the 2015 drought on children's height for age Z-score.

Panel A: Dependent variable: HAZ	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Drought * 2016 round (β_2)	-0.055 (0.170)	-0.027 (0.172)	-0.096 (0.166)	-0.077 (0.168)
Drought (β_1)	0.092 (0.147)	n/a	0.092 (0.141)	n/a
Child and household level controls	No	No	Yes	Yes
Survey round and region interaction terms	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
EA fixed effects?	No	Yes	No	Yes
R ²	0.022	n/a	0.048	n/a
Within-R ²	n/a	0.007	n/a	0.027
Number of observations	3582	3582	3582	3582
Panel B: Dependent variable: WHZ	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
Drought * 2016 round (β_2)	0.166 (0.142)	0.227 (0.157)	0.136 (0.143)	0.208 (0.157)
Drought (β_1)	0.074 (0.114)	n/a	0.060 (0.114)	n/a
Child and household level controls	No	No	Yes	Yes
Survey round and region interaction terms	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
EA fixed effects?	No	Yes	No	Yes
R ²	0.057	n/a	0.071	n/a
Within-R ²	n/a	0.012	n/a	0.022
Number of observations	3582	3582	3582	3582

Notes: Based on Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression method. Unit of observation is a child 6–59-months. Standard errors clustered at the Enumeration Area (EA) level in parentheses. Statistical significance noted at *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

the (null) hypothesis that the 2015 drought had no impact on children's (age and sex adjusted) heights. However, the confidence intervals around the estimates are wide. In our preferred specification based on full set of controls and reported in column 4, the 95%-confidence interval is [-0.407; 0.254].

In panel B, we use WHZ as our outcome variable. The coefficient is counter-intuitively positive but remains statistically

insignificant across all specifications.²⁰ As before, the confidence intervals are wide: in column 4, the 95%-confidence interval is [-0.102; 0.518].

In Table 5 we look at stunting and wasting instead of HAZ and WHZ. Here the outcome variable obtains a value of 1 if child's HAZ

²⁰ The p-values range between 0.148 and 0.344 across the four columns in Panel B.

Table 5
The impact of the 2015 drought on child stunting and wasting.

Panel A: Dependent variable: =1 child is stunted, 0 otherwise	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Drought * 2016 round (β_2)	0.033 (0.046)	0.013 (0.046)	0.042 (0.045)	0.023 (0.046)
Drought (β_1)	-0.039 (0.038)	n/a	-0.031 (0.036)	n/a
Child and household level controls	No	No	Yes	Yes
Survey round and region interaction terms	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
EA fixed effects?	No	Yes	No	Yes
R ²	0.024	n/a	0.047	n/a
Within-R ²	n/a	0.006	n/a	0.021
Number of observations	3582	3582	3582	3582
Panel B: Dependent variable: =1 child is wasted, 0 otherwise	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Drought * 2016 round (β_2)	-0.009 (0.029)	-0.011 (0.031)	-0.007 (0.029)	-0.010 (0.031)
Drought (β_1)	-0.026 (0.023)	n/a	-0.020 (0.022)	n/a
Child and household level controls	No	No	Yes	Yes
Survey round and region interaction terms	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
EA fixed effects?	No	Yes	No	Yes
R ²	0.026	n/a	0.036	n/a
Within-R ²	n/a	0.007	n/a	0.013
Number of observations	3582	3582	3582	3582

Notes: Based on Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression method. Unit of observation is a child 6–59-months. Standard errors clustered at the Enumeration Area (EA) level in parentheses. Statistical significance noted at *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

(for stunting) or WHZ (for wasting) is below -2 , and zero otherwise. In panel A (stunting), the coefficient is small (ranging between 3 and 4 percentage points) and not statistically different from zero with the 95%-confidence interval at $[-0.067; 0.112]$ for the β_2 estimate reported in column 4. The results in panel B (wasting) are similar: the β_2 estimate is small and not statistically significant. The 95%-confidence interval in column 4 is $[-0.071; 0.051]$.

We explored the robustness of these findings in several ways. Previous research shows that findings can be sensitive to how we define drought (Sohnesen, 2019). Therefore, in Appendix B we show that our core findings are remarkably robust to a host of different drought definitions. Same is true for applying sampling weights in the regressions (Appendix C). Moreover, we find no evidence that some child age groups were affected (Appendix D) or that the results were different for boys and girls (Appendix E). We find no evidence that the drought had an impact on children's weight for age – a composite index of height-for-age and weight-for-height (Appendix F). We successfully replicated our null-findings using two rounds of nationally representative Demographic and Health Survey (DHS) data from 2011 and 2016 (Appendix G). Finally, in Appendix H, we provide evidence that our results are unlikely to be biased because of selective attrition of children under 5 due to the drought.

6. Heterogeneity by road access

The foregoing results imply that the 2015 drought did not lead to widespread increases in child undernutrition rates in the country. However, for some of our treatment estimates in Tables 4 and 5, the confidence intervals are wide and include values that would constitute biologically meaningful impacts. This prompts us to explore heterogeneity of our results across road access. The reason for exploring heterogeneity along this dimension is motivated by recent literature on this topic in Ethiopia and elsewhere. Over the past decade, the Ethiopian government has invested heavily in improving the road infrastructure in the country (Minten, Stifel, & Tamru, 2014). Better road networks are typically associated with lower transactions costs for traders to move food across

the country (Minten & Kyle, 1999; Khandker, Bakht, & Koolwal, 2009).²¹ Using data from Nepal and Uganda, Shively (2017) shows how better transportation infrastructure mitigates the negative impact of rainfall shocks on child nutrition. The econometric evidence presented by Hill and Fuje (2016) suggests that past weather shocks in Ethiopia had a smaller impact on grain prices in districts (woredas) that saw improvements in road infrastructure compared to those that did not. Shively and Thapa (2017) find similar evidence from Nepal.²²

We use two measures of road access to explore heterogeneity across road access. First, we use the density of the primary roads (or highways) in woredas.²³ Fig. 11 in Appendix I shows the primary road distribution across the 236 rural woredas in our sample. We see that more than 50 percent of the woredas have no primary roads. To explore whether the impact of the drought varies by the road network in the district, we split the sample into woredas that have no primary road network and woredas with some primary road network.²⁴ We then re-estimated Eq. (1) by interacting this binary road density variable (I_w) with the treatment variable:

$$Y_{irwt} = \beta_1 D_{irw} + \beta_2 (T_t * D_{irw}) + \beta_3 (D_{irw} * I_w) + \beta_4 (T_t * D_{irw} * I_w) + \beta_5 (T_t * I_w) + (T_t * R_t)' \delta + X'_{irw} \gamma + \omega + \varepsilon_{irwt} \quad (2)$$

where ($D_{irw} * I_w$) is an interaction term between the drought shock variable and road access indicator obtaining a value 1 if the woreda in which community c is located has primary roads and zero otherwise. The term ($T_t * D_{irw} * I_w$) is a three-way interaction between the time dummy, drought indicator and road access indicator. To con-

²¹ Poor infrastructure may also delay and increase the cost of the delivery of humanitarian aid.

²² Previous work from rural Ethiopia finds that improvements in road infrastructure are associated with better consumption outcomes and food security (Dercon, Gilligan, Hoddinott, & Woldehanna, 2009; Stifel et al., 2016).

²³ These road densities were calculated from ©OpenStreetMap contributors. The map data is copyrighted to OpenStreetMap contributors and available from <https://www.openstreetmap.org>.

²⁴ 63% of the children in drought-exposed areas resided in districts with some primary roads. The corresponding figure for children who resided in un-exposed areas is 54%.

Table 6
Impact of the 2015 drought on child anthropometric outcomes by district primary road density.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Dependent variable:	HAZ	Child is stunted	WHZ	Child is wasted
Drought * 2016 round (β_2)	-0.457* (0.239)	0.131** (0.064)	0.416** (0.209)	-0.037 (0.045)
Drought * 2016 round * better road access (β_4)	0.657** (0.310)	-0.186** (0.083)	-0.372 (0.281)	0.046 (0.059)
2016 round * better road access (β_5)	-0.047 (0.179)	0.031 (0.046)	-0.073 (0.131)	-0.005 (0.027)
Child and household level controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Survey round and region interaction terms	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
EA fixed effects?	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
F-test ($\beta_2 + \beta_4$)	p = 0.349	p = 0.344	p = 0.829	p = 0.824
Within-R ²	0.028	0.022	0.024	0.013
Number of observations	3582	3582	3582	3582

Notes: Based on Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression method. Unit of observation is a child 6–59-months. Standard errors clustered at the Enumeration Area (EA) level in parentheses. Statistical significance noted at *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1. Better road access = district with primary roads.

Table 7
Impact of the 2015 drought on child anthropometric outcomes by household remoteness indicator based on travel time to urban areas.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Dependent variable:	HAZ	Child is stunted	WHZ	Child is wasted
Drought * 2016 round (β_2)	-0.615* (0.339)	0.145* (0.076)	0.118 (0.253)	0.015 (0.058)
Drought * 2016 round * better road access (β_4)	0.740* (0.392)	-0.170* (0.088)	0.078 (0.284)	-0.032 (0.063)
2016 round * better road access (β_5)	-0.150 (0.184)	0.041 (0.045)	0.124 (0.130)	-0.003 (0.028)
Child and household level controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Survey round and region interaction terms	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
EA fixed effects?	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
F-test ($\beta_2 + \beta_4$)	p = 0.534	p = 0.648	p = 0.287	p = 0.630
Within-R ²	0.028	0.022	0.023	0.013
Number of observations	3582	3582	3582	3582

Notes: Based on Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression method. Unit of observation is a child 6–59-months. Standard errors clustered at the Enumeration Area (EA) level in parentheses. Statistical significance noted at *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1. Better road access = community travel time to urban area is below the sample mean.

control for differences in time trends between well and less well connected areas, we also interact the road access indicator with the time dummy: ($T_t * I_w$). Coefficient β_2 now captures the drought impact in localities with poor road access and the sum of coefficients β_2 and β_4 the impact in better connected localities.

We also tested the parallel trends assumption for this specification. To this end, [Table 11 in Appendix I](#) estimates Eq. (2) using pre-drought data from the 2012 and 2014 ESS rounds. The coefficient on the interaction term is not statistically significant indicating that we cannot reject the null hypothesis that the two areas were on a similar trend before the 2015 drought.

[Table 6](#) provides the results. We find that the 2015 drought increased child undernutrition rates in districts characterized by poor primary road network. In these districts, HAZ scores declined, on average, by 0.5 units of standard deviation because of the drought ($p = 0.057$). The corresponding impact on stunting is about 13 percentage points ($p = 0.042$). Meanwhile, the F-tests show that the estimated impacts on HAZ and stunting are not statistically different from zero in districts that had a relatively better road network. Interestingly, we find no evidence that the drought reduced WHZ or increased wasting prevalence. However, the estimates in column 3 indicate that WHZ increased in districts with poor road network. This improvement in the WHZ could be a result of a weight gain after a period of slow growth in height. [Schoenbuchner et al. \(2019\)](#) call this as body's 'internal adjustment' where resources are diverted away from increasing overall body size (i.e., height) to tissue accretion (i.e., weight gain).

As an alternative measure of road access, we use the recently developed estimates on travel time to the nearest urban centers

([Weiss et al., 2018](#)) and link these to our household survey data using community level GPS coordinates. The mean travel time to the nearest urban center in our sample is 105 min. The road access indicator in Eq. (2) now obtains a value 1 if the travel time is above the mean (105 min) and zero otherwise. [Table 7](#) presents the regression results. As before, we find that children residing in households located in more remote areas were negatively affected by the drought whereas children located in better connected areas were not. In remote communities, HAZ scores declined, on average, by 0.6 units of standard deviation because of the drought. The corresponding estimated impact for stunting is 14.5 percentage points. The sums of the two first coefficients within each column are close to zero suggesting that the droughts impacts on HAZ (column 1) and stunting (column 2) were negligible in more connected localities. F-tests further confirm the sums of these estimates are not statistically different from zero. This time we see no heterogeneous impacts (positive or negative) on measures of acute undernutrition (WHZ or wasting).

7. Conclusions

We do not find evidence that the 2015 drought in Ethiopia led to widespread increases in chronic or acute child undernutrition. This finding is remarkably robust to using a wide variety of different drought indicators as well as using other large national level data set. Our further analysis highlights the mitigating role of road networks. The null-result documented in this paper seems to originate from districts that had a relatively better road network. When we look at heterogeneity along this dimension, we find that

the 2015 drought increased chronic undernutrition rates in districts that had a poor road network.

This study has limitations. First, the anthropometric measures were taken about six months after the drought. It is reasonable to ask whether we should expect a drought to influence linear growth within such a short time-frame. The available evidence from seasonal anthropometric surveys in rural Ethiopia indicate that rapid changes in children's growth outcomes do occur. In an earlier study, Lindtjørn and Alemu (2002) took more than 5,500 repeated anthropometric measurements from 678 children in Oromia region over a six year period. The authors document large and erratic seasonal variations in stunting, especially among children less than 2 years of age. Another study from Tigray and Oromia showed how child stunting prevalence increased from 40 percent to 46 percent in just over a six month period (Roba et al., 2016). Using high-frequency longitudinal survey in which the same households in Tigray region were visited seven times over a 24-month period, Berhane et al. (2015) document sizeable fluctuations in child stunting prevalence, ranging from less than one percentage points to more than eight percentage points between two adjacent survey rounds. Moreover, international evidence indicates that nutritional interventions lasting less than 6 months can result in sizable improvements in child growth outcomes during the first 5 years of life (Imdad & Bhutta, 2011; Roberts and Stein, 2017). Nevertheless, we cannot be sure whether our findings would have been different had we had anthropometric data from these localities 12 or 18 months after the drought occurred.²⁵

Second, given the data available to us, we are not able to convincingly carry out an analysis on the role of aid in mitigating the negative impacts on child nutrition. Indeed, conducting rigorous impact assessments of assistance in humanitarian contexts is difficult (Puri et al., 2017) because the selection into humanitarian assistance is not random. Rather, it is likely that the aid is allocated to the poorest and most vulnerable households – or to those that are on a downward trajectory along these dimensions. It is plausible that the humanitarian response during 2015/16 played an important role in mitigating the impact of the drought on child undernutrition. Some observers note that the humanitarian response during the 2015 drought was particularly strong and effective (Babu, Rutishauser-Perera, & Prudhon, 2017; De Waal, 2017; Tucker Brown & Ategbo, 2017). According to AKLDP (2016), the Government of Ethiopia distributed more than 600,000 tons of food aid between August and December 2015 to the drought exposed areas in Afar, Amhara, Oromia and Tigray regions. Considerable effort was also directed into monitoring and treatment of children suffering from severe acute malnutrition (SAM). Babu et al. (2017) estimate that about 13 million children were screened during the drought. This is nearly four times the amount screened in 2011 (3.35 million children) – the last time Ethiopia suffered a large-scale drought.²⁶

These limitations aside, our study provides useful insights into building resilience against droughts. This is important, as due to global warming, severe droughts are likely to become more frequent in Africa, including Ethiopia. Increase in the drought frequency is likely put the financing of the humanitarian response system into considerable stress, possibly risking the sufficient financing of humanitarian aid in the future (The World Bank, 2017). Our results give suggestive evidence that investments in sectors that support development and economic growth (here road infrastructure) may also assist in building long-term resilience

against droughts, thereby decreasing the share of people in need of food aid.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2020.104964>.

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²⁵ Unfortunately, 2016 was the last round of the ESS panel survey that began in 2012.

²⁶ SAM cases were largely managed at the community level building on the existing Health Extension Programme platform.

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